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LINGUISTIC FOUNDATIONS OF RHETORIC AND THE FORMATION OF SCIENTIFIC SPEECH ON ITS BASIS.

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the linguistic features of rhetorical sentences and rhetorical discourse in scientifically oriented speech from the point of view of scientific and theoretical understanding of this paradigm. The semantics of rhetorical statements is multilevel - from logical-semantic categorical: affirmation, denial, reasoning (with a branched gradation) to situational: agreement, objection, confirmation, hesitation, reflection, etc. The main feature of the main, communicative, function of a rhetorical statement is the transfer of information to expressive, figurative form. The logical content of the sentence "I know" can be conveyed in rhetorical statements: Why don't I know? I know; - How not to know?; Don't know?; How can you think (assume, imagine) that I don't know?; Who knows if not me? The choice of rhetorical variations to convey a certain communicative meaning is determined by the speech situation. "The linguistic meaning of this statement is understood against the background of the language, its actual meaning - against the background of other specific statements on the same topic, against the background of conflicting opinions, points of view and assessments." The stability, reproducibility of the rhetorical form determines the well-known constancy of the lexical composition, and, consequently, the aphoristic nature of rhetorical statements of various types (advice, recommendations, moralizing): Isn't it better to turn on yourself, godfather? (I. Krylov).

Language is a complex social phenomenon; it is a system of movement and development. As a means of communication, language exists to convey socially significant information. It

expresses the accumulation of human knowledge, the achievements of civilization, volitional impulses, sensory and emotional states.

The language was created to meet the needs of society and to best serve human communication in various areas of social life. These and other areas of communication are served by a certain set of speech means. They serve various aspects of human life and activity, which differ from each other in specific features that arise due to differences in the subject, purpose of speech, speaker and communication conditions. Usually they are divided into five main functional styles: scientific, official business, journalistic, colloquial and artistic. In order to demonstrate the diversity of the stylistic possibilities of the language depending on the communicative situation, goals and objectives, this book focuses on two styles: scientific and formal business.

The language of scientific and technical literature, due to its peculiarities, is distinguished by another style, the so-called "scientific manner of speech".

From the point of view of rhetorical discourse, science as a form of social consciousness is characterized by the desire for the most accurate, logical and unambiguous expression of thought. The main form of thinking in science is conceptual, and the linguistic embodiment of the dynamism of thought is expressed in the form of judgments and conclusions. The purpose of science is to identify patterns. Thus, it is a generalized and abstract way of thinking. The main characteristics of scientific speech are objectivity, abstractness, intelligence and brevity. There are several sub-styles in the scientific system of speech.

Correct scientific (academic) - used for writing scientific papers and articles; scientific and information or scientific and business style - the style of patent or

technical writing; educational - a substyle of scientific - educational literature; popular science and so on.

Main part

The characteristics of the scientific style are the accuracy of the transmitted information, the persuasiveness of the argument, the logical coherence of the presentation and the concise format, focused on the addressee - the expert. Communication between an expert and a non-specialist leads to the organization of language tools that are separated from the purely scientific style. Scientific data should be presented in an understandable and entertaining form that does not simplify science and at the same time does not overload the presentation with complex material, and another substyle of scientific speech is born - popular science substyle.

The scientific and business substyle occupies a particularly important place. Very strict requirements are imposed on scientific and business correspondence: fixed composition, maximum standardization of language means, uniformity of syntactic structure. The main purpose of this kind of literature is to convey scientific information that is the most accurate and objective description of the facts available, and (more importantly) legally protect this information.

The educational-scientific sub-style differs from other sub-styles of scientific literature mainly in that the target audience is not experts, but future experts. Thematically, this type of scientific literature is limited to the presentation of the foundations of science. It is educational in nature, full of definitions, examples, comparisons, explanations and interpretations. Scientific speech, like writing, has developed over a

long period of time, and the style of scientific speech accepted today was formed at the beginning of the 20th century. For comparison, we give an example from the work of M.V. Lomonosov, which is now called "On Security". He says: "This man, dressed in wet sails, with a burning candle on a long stick, forked at one end, goes on his belly to the most terrible place in the hole, and, having approached the place where this burning air is, the air immediately ignites. with a crack like a cannon shot, and he comes out of the hole. As long as the air is clear and close to the face, no great harm or any damage is done to the person.

Linguistic features of the scientific, rhetorical style in the section of linguistics. Morphology, syntax, vocabulary and word structure. The greatest need of the language of science is vocabulary. The vocabulary of scientific speech differs significantly from others in the presence of terminology. A term is a word, phrase or abbreviation denoting a certain scientific concept in a specific terminological system or science. Terms are subject to special conditions. The term should be unambiguous and stylistically neutral. The term itself is a familiar and conventional sign of this science.

Vectors, integrals, dissociation, hydrolysis, etc. are used as terms as well as loanwords. For example, in geology and mining there are many terms of Russian origin, such as deposit, vein, compression, bending, tension, strength, roof (or roof) of the reservoir, bottom of the reservoir. The last two examples (roof, bottom layer) illustrate how words are finalized in common written languages. Even the richest languages have limited resources. Languages are forced to distribute a huge

number of new scientific concepts in the form of ready-made language units. The formation of terms follows the unfolding of the polysemy of words. Examples: earth's crust, waste rock, quarry.

Grammatical features of scientific speech. Studies have shown that the language of science is characterized by amazing selectivity and stability in the use of various morphological categories, word forms, phrases and types of sentences that create the "morphological and syntactic face" of this subspecies of the written language. The preference for certain morphological categories is not limited to a particular science, but is a characteristic feature of scientific and technical terminology in general.

The language of science is nominative; science is naming and defining. The language of science is dominated by nouns and adjectives, and verbs fade into the background.

Morphological selectivity affects not only the distribution of parts of speech, but also the distribution of their meanings.

In scientific speech, the genitive case is most often used. In modern Russian, as is known, word forms with several meanings are characteristic, especially in the genitive, dative and prepositional cases. In the scientific field, however, case forms can have only a very limited number of meanings. The genitive case develops predominantly determinative relations in the scientific field, accounting for up to 40% of uses. This is evidenced by its widespread use in proper names, such as Newton's laws, the periodic table, Gauss's theorem, and in phrases such as the force of friction, gravity, the law of refraction of light, the theory of complex numbers.

The genitive case is quite common in combination with verbal nouns such as the production of gamma rays and the concept of infinitesimals. A characteristic feature of these phrases is that they can form a chain of genitive cases, which allows you to accurately name the object of study.

Consider the selective meaning of the infinitive case. In colloquial and artistic styles, they are most often combined with the prepositions about, in and on. In the scientific style, the prepositional case is often used with the preposition at, which has a conditional/temporal meaning, for example, in heating, shaping, burying, underground coal mining, etc. Synonyms with this meaning are also used with which, with that.

The same selective tendency of meaning is manifested in the use of verbs. Verbs "lose" part of their meaning and specialize in using only one, rarely two meanings. The most frequently used verbs in the languages of various sciences are "influence", "arise", "increase", "confirm", "depend", "change", "measure", "be", "use", "distinguish", "fit" and "evolve".

The vast majority of verbs in scientific conversation are either completely or partially deverbilized. That is, the verb loses its basic meaning and functions as a link. For example, to be, to be called, to become, to remain, to count, to have, to differ, to be defined, to conclude, to compose, to serve, to express, to characterize, etc.

Verb morphemes also indicate the selective use of time. Most verbs are used in the present imperfect tense. Thus, the timeless, attributive (determinative) meaning of the verb is expressed, or constancy, immutability, or the actual meaning of the action.

A feature of the syntax of scientific speech is that the discrepancy between the syntactic level of the sentence and the logical level of grammar is less than in other styles, the syntactic level is largely "adapted" to the need to express the logical structure of thought. The analysis shows the divergence of subordination and the complication of syntax, when sentences "attach" to each other, as if blocked, creating a syntax not found in other styles and guaranteeing clear syntagmatic connections and a clear structural organization even over long periods of time.

The coherence of a sentence is created with the help of various linguistic means. In addition to conjunctions and participles, pronouns are used, such as the desired angle, in this case, the above refers to, from the previously known, we indicate the following, for this purpose, on this basis, and so on, for example, adjectives and participles. These means of communication are called "capacitive language". Scientific writing uses 34 connected units per 100 sentences, while fiction uses 18 connected units.

Scientific speech has the following qualities.

- Objectivity (different points of view, lack of subjectivity, impersonal language expressions, focus on the subject)
- Logic (connectedness, sequence) (special constructions) (complex sentences with adjectives causes, conditions and consequences, sentences with introductory words first, finally, therefore, so on, etc.) and typical means of interclass communication (repetition, synonyms)
- Justification (chains of reasoning, argumentation of statements and hypotheses).

- Accuracy (use of terms, unambiguous language);
- Generalization and abstraction (a chain of reasoning and argumentation of a statement or hypothesis);
- Accuracy (use of terms, unambiguous language, etc.).

- Generalization and abstraction (abstraction).

A) the choice of words (the predominance of nouns over verbs, general scientific terms, nouns with an abstract meaning; B) the use of word forms (verbs in the present tense with the meaning "out of time", recursive and impersonal verbs, the predominance of third person verb forms, imperfect tense), use of syntax (indefinitely personal sentences, passive sentences).

- Saturation with factual information.

- The presence of many technical terms.

There are several sub-styles in the system of scientific speech.

- scientific (academic) - used for writing scientific articles and dissertations.

- academic - a substyle of educational literature (the logical coherence of topics and a gradually developing way of expressing "compressed completeness", which is expressed, on the one hand, in the fact that only part of the information accumulated on the subject of science is presented, and on the other hand, in the fact that this the part is fundamental and describes the topic being presented in a uniform and voluminous way (see below).

- Popular science (information should not oversimplify science and should be presented in a friendly and entertaining

way, at the same time not overloading the presentation with hard-to-reach material)

- Scientific-informative or scientific-business eloquence is the style of a patent or technical description.

Conclusion

Reasoning in a scientific conversation has a variant form of evidence. Both types of writing have a compositional scheme premise (thesis) - argument - conclusion. The difference between a conclusion and a proof is that in a conclusion a new conclusion that was not in the premises may appear in the conclusion, while in a proof the conclusion is either confirmed or refuted by the argument, i.e. The conclusion repeats or refutes the thesis.

The above features of scientific speech constitute the specifics of the scientific style as a whole, due to the distribution of grammatical categories and lexical-semantic specialization based on the rhetorical component of constructing a beautiful, official, scientific speech. The terminology is universal and is used in Russian scientific texts in various natural and technical fields.

As for the last aspect of this study, namely the extralinguistic features of scientific speech, when considering the extralinguistic features of scientific speech, the units of observation were words and phrases. Extralinguistic features of style should be discussed by analyzing the design and expression of thought. The observation units are paragraph and text.

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